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The transcriptional landscape of normal-like subtype breast cancer in humans: NECAP2.

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Breast cancer in humans is a solid tumor type with distinct subtypes historically defined by the PAM50 molecular subtype classification scheme (1-3). We utilize, in this study, whole transcriptome technologies to define the transcriptional landscape of normal-like subtype human breast cancer (4, 5). We describe here differential expression of NECAP2 in the subtype of human breast cancer known as normal-like.

We harnessed the power of whole transcriptome technology, using only primary tumor tissues from patients with breast cancer of defined molecular subtype (4, 5) to perform differential gene expression analyses, for characterization, in molecular detail, of the tumor transcriptome of normal-like subtype breast cancer.

Methods

We utilized microarray datasets GSE41119 (4) and GSE87049 (5) for this global differential gene expression analysis of normal-like subtype human breast cancer in conjunction with the R-based computational differential gene expression software GEO2R. GSE41119 was generated using UNC PerouLab 244K Custom Human Array (version 5) technology with $n=10$ normal breast tissues (control) and $n=5$ normal-like subtype primary tumors from humans with breast cancer; analysis was performed using GPL8269. GSE87049 was generated using Affymetrix Human Gene 1.0 ST Array [transcript (gene) version] technology with $n=35$ normal breast tissues (control) $n=14$ primary breast tumors of normal-like subtype from humans with breast cancer; analysis was performed using platform GPL6244. We used an R-based bioinformatic tool to perform whole transcriptome co-regulation studies across multiple tissues (SEEK [6]). We utilized a computational tool to measure the influence of tumor gene expression on overall survival in humans with breast cancer, in $n=1879$ patients (total), in $n=431$ basal subtype patients, in $n=596$ luminal A subtype patients, in $n=439$ luminal B subtype patients, in $n=362$ HER2+ patients, and $n=51$ normal-like subtype patients (7).

Rationale

Breast cancer in humans is a complex molecular entity that remains to be completely defined.

Results

We performed whole transcriptome profiling - subtraction analysis, also known as differential gene expression profiling - to identify and describe at the systems level the complete set of genes whose expression was most specifically activated or repressed in humans with the normal-like subtype of human breast cancer.

1. Primary tumors of the breast from humans with breast cancer: normal-like subtype

$n=10$ normal breast tissues (human)

$n=5$ primary tumors (breast; human; normal-like)

ID	<i>p</i> -value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
7713	4.79E-04	-4.55	0.1326989	-6.51E-01	NECAP2	2549/243504	99.0

Through quantitative comparison of total transcription in normal breast tissues and normal-like breast tumors, we discovered differential expression of NECAP endocytosis associated 2, encoded by NECAP2 (located at 1p36.13) in normal-like breast cancer in humans (Chart 1). The expression of NECAP2 changed more than 99% of the human breast and breast tumor transcriptome when considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 243,504 transcripts ("Rank"). Note the negative fold-change indicating increased quantity of NECAP2 messenger RNA in normal-like subtype tumors, demonstrating up-regulation of NECAP2 during transformation of the breast from normal breast tissue to normal-like breast cancer.

2. Primary tumors of the breast from humans with breast cancer: normal-like subtype

$n=35$ normal breast tissues (human)

$n=14$ primary tumors (breast; human; normal-like)

ID	<i>p</i> -value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
7898337	3.21E-04	-3.863166	0.1742	-0.4116194	NECAP2	1298/33297	96.1

Through quantitative comparison of total transcription in normal breast tissues and normal-like breast tumors in a second microarray dataset from independent investigators and a separate patient cohort, we validated differential expression of NECAP2 in normal-like breast cancer in humans (Chart 2). The expression of NECAP2 here changed more than 96% of the human breast and breast tumor transcriptome when considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 33,297 transcripts (“Rank”). Note the negative fold-change indicating increased quantity of NECAP2 messenger RNA in normal-like subtype tumors, demonstrating up-regulation of NECAP2 during transformation of the breast from normal breast tissue to normal-like subtype breast cancer.

Thus, NECAP2 is a gene whose differential expression defines the transcriptional landscape of the normal-like breast cancer subtype in humans.

In breast cancer as in any solid tumor, the function of the gene identified by whole transcriptome differential gene expression cannot be assumed to be the same as in non-transformed tissues. Thus, to identify gene products likely to interact with and/or be relevant to the differentially expressed genes function in the transformed tissue, we performed whole transcriptome transcriptional co-regulation studies using SEEK, an R-based computational tool that blindly and quantitatively identifies co-expression across the genome using a clustering method rather than integration-based differential gene expression methodology (6). This second whole transcriptome technology identified HLA-E, CAP1, CAPZB, HLA-B and PPP1R18 as the five genes across the transcriptome most closely co-regulated with NECAP2 in the transformed human breast (**Figure 1**).

Figure 1: Transcriptional co-regulation in the transformed human breast: NECAP2.

1 Finally, we measured the influence of NECAP2 tumor gene expression on overall survival in
 2 humans with breast cancer (**Figure 2**) (7).

18 **Fig. 2: Relationship between NECAP2 tumor expression and overall survival in humans with breast cancer.**
 19 Caption: Overall survival in all patients (above; left), in patients with basal subtype (above; center), in patients with luminal A
 20 subtype (above; right), in patients with luminal B subtype (below; left), in patients with HER2+ subtype (below; center), and
 21 patients with normal-like subtype breast cancer (below; right) is depicted in these Kaplan-Meier plots.

22 **Discussion**

23 We describe here NECAP2 as a component gene product of normal-like subtype in human breast
 24 cancer, suggesting its importance in the development or maintenance of the subtype, a product of tumor
 25 evolution in transformation of solid tissues in humans.
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